

The Theory and Practice of 5D BIM Model for Construction Project Management

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Abstract

This paper explores 5D BIM for construction project management from a theoretical and practical standpoint. Building information modeling (BIM), which enables designers, engineers, contractors, and other team members to more efficiently cooperate using a single digital model of the building, has changed the construction business. In 5D BIM, the two additional dimensions of time and money further improve the model's functionality by allowing for more precise cost estimating, cost control, and project scheduling. This research looks on the main advantages and difficulties of using 5D BIM in building project management. The research assesses how 5D BIM may boost project efficiency, lower risks, and improve project results through a detailed literature review and case studies. It looks on the main advantages and difficulties of using 5D BIM in building project management. The article discovers the various technologies and software tools available for 5D BIM modeling and reviews their capabilities, benefits, and drawbacks. The paper finishes with a list of suggestions, including training programs, communication protocols, and project management approaches, for successfully using 5D BIM in construction project management. Overall, this research offers insightful information about the theory and application of 5D BIM for construction project management, emphasizing its potential to revolutionize the sector and enhance project results.

Keywords: *Building Information Modeling (BIM), Project Management, Schedule, Cost, 3D BIM, 4D BM, 5D BIM, Revit, Navisworks.*

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Introduction

Background and Significance of 5D BIM

A digital method named Building Information Modeling (BIM) makes it easier to create, share,

and manage data throughout the lifecycle of a building project. A development of BIM known as 5D BIM includes the integration of cost and schedule data into the 3D model. In other words, 5D BIM is the incorporation of time and cost dimensions with the 3D model to provide

an even more powerful and complete tool for management building projects.

Because it can deliver accurate cost and schedule information early in the project lifecycle, 5D BIM is important for construction project management. It helps construction industry staff make well-informed decisions, detect potential problems, and better manage risks. This will lead to a reduced project costs and delivery time, as well as an increase in project productivity and quality.

The collaboration and communication between project stakeholders, such as owners, architects, engineers, contractors, and suppliers, can also be improved by 5D BIM. Improved project outcomes may result from greater project integration and coordination of design, construction, and operation activities.

Given the potential advantages of 5D BIM, the building sector has begun using it more frequently. Therefore, in order for construction professionals to properly utilize 5D BIM and produce successful project outcomes, it is imperative that they have a solid understanding of both its theory and application.

Research Aims and Objectives

Research aim of this paper is to investigate the possible advantages of using a 5D BIM model for construction project management.

Objectives are:

1. To perform an evaluation of the literature on BIM, its development, the 5D BIM model, and its application to construction project management.
2. To determine the advantages and difficulties of employing a 5D BIM model in the management of construction projects.
3. To conduct research into how frequently the 5D BIM model is being used for project management in the construction industry.
4. To evaluate effectively implementing a 5D BIM model effects project budget, schedule, quality, and risk control.
5. To evaluate the extent to which project participants, such as contractors, designers, and clients, have an understanding of and trained in

the use of the 5D BIM model in construction project management.

Literature Review

Building information modeling, usually 5D BIM, is the process of using BIM technology to add cost-related information into the design of constructions. This contains data that can be included in the 3D model and examined during the course of the project lifetime, such as the project budget, material costs, and labor expenses.

The 5D BIM adds time and cost as additional dimensions in addition to the conventional 3D model. This indicates that the model takes into account both the geographical connections between building elements as well as the timing of construction activities and their financial effects.

The advantages of 5D BIM include greater cost management, more effective building process efficiency, and improved stakeholder participation. Project teams are able to better understand the monetary effects of design decisions and make more informed decisions by including cost-related data into the model. The theory behind 5D BIM represents a more comprehensive approach to building modeling, one that takes into account not only the physical aspects of the building but also the time and cost implications of the construction process. Additionally, 5D BIM allows for real-time cost monitoring and forecasting, which can help prevent budget overruns and delays.

Overall, 5D BIM offers a potent tool for managing building projects, allowing stakeholders to work well together, plan and improve resources, and complete projects more quickly and successfully.

An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of the 5D BIM Model in Improving Construction Project Management

Building information modelling (BIM) is now a crucial tool for managing and planning building projects. The 5D BIM model is a variation of BIM that includes time and cost dimensions to the 3D model, introducing extra information to the planning and administration of the

construction process. In this evaluation, we'll look at how effectively the 5D BIM model has helped construction project management.

The reality that the 5D BIM model offers a thorough perspective of the project's schedule, cost, and progress is one of its key benefits. Making educated judgements and modifications throughout the construction project depends on this knowledge. The project team can use the model to prepare for possible issues before they develop and make the necessary adjustments before, they get worse.

The 5D BIM model can also significantly benefit construction projects by reducing waste and inefficiencies. The team can plan and optimize the construction process, minimizing waste and increasing efficiency, through developing a comprehensive model that covers every area of the project. This may consequently result in lower costs and faster project completion times.

The collaboration between project stakeholders, such as architects, engineers, contractors, and owners, can be enhanced by the 5D BIM model. The concept offers a common forum for successful collaboration and communication among all stakeholders, lowering the possibility of misunderstandings and mistakes.

The 5D BIM model can also contribute to increased safety on construction sites. By offering a thorough model, the team is able recognize potential safety risks and take the appropriate safety measures to protect employees.

Despite the benefits, putting the 5D BIM model into practice has certain difficulties. The absence of industry-wide standardization is one of the major problems. As a result, collaboration amongst various stakeholders may be challenging. In addition, there is a learning curve involved with putting the model into practice, which could take more time and money.

As a result, the 5D BIM model can be useful in enhancing construction project management by offering a thorough perspective of the project's schedule, cost, and progress, lowering waste and inefficiencies, enhancing stakeholder participation, and enhancing safety on building sites. However, there are difficulties with the

model's implementation, such as standardization and a learning curve. Overall, the 5D BIM model has the potential to be a useful tool for managing construction projects, and its adoption should be taken into account in the future.

Methodology

This experiment is an example of action research, which does not collect hard data but instead produces outputs for analysis, such as model drawings, schedules, and time lines. Expert reviews are conducted after the results of the action research pilot study. For this pilot study, a representative House is used as a point of reference. The research methodology involves simulating and analyzing the entire 5D BIM with a hands-on approach. Observations are made in order to evaluate the viability of 5D BIM.

The initial step includes collecting and building data into a 3D model. Clients are briefed on their requirements at the beginning of the process, which results in an initial proposal. By combining various fields including civil and structural engineering, mechanical and electrical engineering, and interior design, an architectural proposal is established, and the 3D model is then produced. Each and every component is described in detail in the 3D model.

After the clients are pleased with the original design and it complies with the requirements, the second stage will begin. The information for cost estimation will be entered into the 3D model by quantity surveyors or cost engineers. Automated quantification of building components using unit pricing is used for cost estimation. From the perspective of cost assessment, 4D BIM is quite helpful at this point in helping clients refine their objectives. When the clients are happy with the finished 4D BIM, the third stage will start. Work Breakdown Structures (WBS) will be developed by project managers for all different kinds of building tasks. Due to the BIM integration, a vast quantity of information may be allowed, with WBS including more levels than a typical system. The project time schedule will be impacted by some important elements, including construction method, human resources, material procurement, and supply. At this point, 5D BIM contains all the necessary information. VDC will

be used at the project's final stage to display 5D BIM project components, project costs, and time scheduling

Apparatus

There are many kinds of BIM software on the market. Autodesk Revit is a software program that is often used. Automation and improved stakeholder communication are a couple of Autodesk Revit's advantages.

Autodesk Revit was selected as the modelling platform for this study primarily because to its strong multidisciplinary integration and adjustable automation, both of which are important for 5D BIM process. Revit Architecture and Revit Structure are the only modelling applications available. The hardware configuration is as stated in the Autodesk Revit 2024 system requirements:

- CPU Type: Quad-Core Intel i5-4590S CPU @ 3.00GHz
- Memory: 4 GB RAM
- Video Display: 1,680 x 1,050 with true color.
- Disk Space: minimum 5 GB free disk space.

Collection and Input of Building Information into 3D Model

Competency in integrating pre-BIM data, such as 2D CAD data, will influence how practical BIM is. Even though BIM has grown in popularity over time, certain stakeholders are still learning about this novel technique. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the preliminary data in the form of 2D drawings in order to identify the main grid lines and border lines. The grid lines of the house unit, which are necessary to erect elements such columns, slabs, beams, and walls.

Input of Information for Cost Estimation

BIM is actually one of the best automatic techniques to immediately produce an accurate quantity take off from 3D product models. Automated information extraction of numerous component parameters, such as "Family and Type" and "Volume," is necessary for cost assessment. Quantity surveyors or cost engineers

must then enter the component information for the per-unit "Cost" field. The information about "Cost" per unit is then connected to the "Family and Type" and "Volume" of the components using a formula or percentage computation.

Figure 1. 5D BIM Process Flowchart

Input of Information for Time Scheduling

Similar to 2D CAD, project management with time scheduling is typically carried out using programs like Primavera, Excel, or Microsoft Project. According to the particular WBS, such time scheduling information needs to be

connected to each and every component. This particular time schedule data can be interchanged with BIM software like Autodesk Navisworks Manage, similar to how 2D CAD data can.

Virtualization of 5D Building Information Modelling

The last step is to build an animation or time liner, to clearly convey 5D BIM and meet the needs of all stakeholders. Making comparative VDCs that differ in cost planning, human resource planning, and building methodologies is one of the creative alternatives. For customers and decision-makers to simulate, identify, and troubleshoot uncertainties throughout the entire construction project, this methodology is quite thorough. 5D BIM as-built information virtualization should be carried out to track the gap between the plan and actual progress as construction advances.

Practice Research Area and Bim Implementation Case Study

The research area is a G+3 stores located near Diabetics Hospital in Joypurhat, Bangladesh. The Ground floor are used for parking, and the other floors are used for living, bed room, open terrace etc. A total of 4680 square feet were built up. The entire building plan is created using AUTO CAD software, and Revit 2024 are used for 3D model and cost estimation and Excel and Navisworks used for 4D scheduling.

2D CAD Drawing

For this project at first, I make a 2D CAD drawing using Autodesk AutoCAD 2022, AutoCAD drawings can be easily transferred to Revit and it is much easier for civil engineers to understand.

Figure 2. AutoCAD Floor Plan

Figure 3. AutoCAD Floor Plan with Architecture Futures

3D Structural Building

In the current study, structural building information models are created by translating 2D designs into 3D modelling simulations using REVIT Architecture 2024. Before beginning construction, this enables us to see the interior of the project and make alterations. Here the authors discuss some steps for create 3D Structural Building.

First Open Revit and start a new project. Define the project's units, levels, and other project settings according to requirements.

Figure 4. Set Up Project

Figure 5. Import Base Plan

Begin by importing a 2D floor plan of the building that we want to model. Alternatively, we could be drawing the floor plan directly in Revit using the architectural tools.

Figure 6. Create Levels

Define the building levels (e.g., floors, roofs) based on the imported plan. Assign the appropriate heights to each level.

Figure 7. Build Walls

Using the wall tool to draw the walls of the building. Specify the wall type, height, width, and other properties. Revit allows to create different

wall types with specific materials and thicknesses.

Figure 8. Define Materials and Parameters

Assign materials to the building elements such as walls, floors, and ceilings. Specify the properties

of each material, including appearance, thermal properties, and structural characteristics.

Figure 9. Include Other Architectural Elements

Continue adding other architectural elements such as stairs, columns, beams, and roofs as

required. Using the relevant tools and define their properties accurately.

Figure 10. Create Floors and Ceilings

Generate floor and ceiling elements to complete the building structure. Revit provides tools to

create these elements based on the walls and levels that defined.

Figure 11. Add Doors and Windows

Place doors and windows in the walls using the appropriate tools. Specify their sizes, types, and properties. Revit provides a library of pre-

defined door and window families, can also create custom ones if needed.

Figure 12. Add Components and Fixtures

Populate the model with components like furniture, fixtures, lighting, and equipment. I can

use pre-defined families or create custom ones to match project requirements.

Figure 13. Final 3D View and Cross-Section View

4D Scheduling

The REVIT is used for Scheduling. The project's schedule was primarily based on quantity takeoff by creating simulation 3D models. A certain desired level of graphical representation, thorough project planning, and dynamic interaction should all be possible with 4D model scheduling. To create a 4D model in Navisworks some steps are described below:

Figure 14. Shared Parameters

For 4D simulation first we need to create shared parameter, shared parameter is something that can be across the project, this shared parameter

known as Task ID, after getting shared parameter.

Figure 15. Project Parameters

After creating Sheard parameters It's bring to project parameter and change the parameter type that shown in figure 15.

Task ID	Type	Title	Duration	Start Time	Finish Time	
1	1	Construction	Preconstruction	4	6/13/2021	6/17/2021
2	2	Construction	Footings	6	6/17/2021	6/23/2021
3	3	Construction	Grade beams Ground floor	7	6/23/2021	6/30/2021
4	4	Construction	Ground floor stair	3	6/30/2021	7/3/2021
5	5	Construction	Basement Level Pcc	4	7/3/2021	7/7/2021
6	6	Construction	Columns to Ground floor	5	7/7/2021	7/12/2021
7	7	Construction	Basement Ramp	4	7/13/2021	7/17/2021
8	8	Construction	1Compound wall	7	7/18/2021	7/25/2021
9	9	Construction	Lift shaft	5	7/26/2021	7/31/2021
10	10	Construction	Plinth level beam	6	8/1/2021	8/7/2021
11	11	Construction	Plinth level stair	4	8/8/2021	8/12/2021
12	12	Construction	Plinth level slab	7	8/13/2021	8/20/2021
13	13	Construction	Column on First Floor	5	8/21/2021	8/26/2021
14	14	Construction	Ramp on First Floor	6	8/27/2021	9/2/2021

Figure 16. Schedule Excel Sheet.

First need to make a Microsoft Excel schedule, the schedule includes task id, Title, durations, and start/finish dates, and change the file format in CSV than import the project schedule into

Navisworks, Need to determine the duration of each task in the project schedule. This information will help Navisworks simulate the project timeline accurately.

Figure 17. Assign Tasks to Model Elements

Assign tasks from the project schedule to the relevant elements in the 3D model. This can be done by linking each task to specific components

or objects in the model. I use selection and grouping tools in Navisworks to facilitate this process.

Figure 18. Export Revit file to Navisworks nwc Format

Figure 19. Import Excel File to Navisworks

After open the Navisworks file we need to Import the CSV excel file from Data Sources option.

Figure 20. Field Selector

In this field need to select what column of CSV file are match with Time liner, include Title, Task ID, Type, Start/Finish Time.

Figure 21. Animate the Schedule

Use Navisworks' Time Liner feature to create an animation of the project timeline. Adjust the settings to define the simulation duration, frame rate, and camera views. Navisworks will display the model elements as they evolve over time based on the assigned tasks and their durations.

5D Cost Estimation

In order to estimate costs, stakeholders in the estimated regions are contacted and REVIT software is used. If the estimating is carried out by someone who is perfectly matched to some costing workflows, the process is straightforward and controllable. Estimating the quantities takes up a significant amount of time

throughout the cost estimation process, roughly 50% to 80% of the total time needed.

5D cost estimation can be done in many ways, I have mentioned both Revit and Navisworks systems here.

To create a 5D BIM cost analysis in Revit, we need to integrate the cost data with the 3D model and schedule information.

First need to Prepare the Cost Data Gather the cost information for the project, including material costs, labor costs, equipment costs, and any other relevant expenses. Organize the cost data in a spreadsheet or a database.

To Create a Cost Schedule in Revit, go to the View tab and select Schedules, Schedule/Quantities. In the Schedule Properties dialog box, choose the appropriate category (e.g., walls, doors, windows) for which that we want to create the cost schedule. Customize the

schedule to include the necessary cost parameters, such as material cost, labor cost, etc.

Figure 22. Fields Selection for Schedule

For Schedule first need to select fields that we want show in schedule and assign formula.

Figure 23. Formula Setup for Wall Material Takeoff

For wall material takeoff need to assign formula that is total volume/size of brick.

Figure 24 Wall Material Takeoff

Figure 25. Wall Schedule with Total Cost

This Cost is including Material and labor cost, and the formula is unit price *cost.

Figure 26. Column Material Takeoff and Cost

Figure 27. Parameter for Roof and Cost

Figure 28. Roof Schedule with Total Cost

<Door Schedule>		
A	B	
Family and Type	Cost	
Door-Exterior-Double-Full Glass-Wood_Clad:3'9"	15220: Door-Exterior-Double-Full GI	\$150.00
Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 17605:	Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:	\$120.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 17684:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 17684	\$100.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84":	Single-Flush:30" x 84"	\$90.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 2:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 2	\$100.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 3:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 3	\$100.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 4:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 4	\$100.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 5:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 5	\$100.00
Single-Flush:30" x 84" 6:	Single-Flush:30" x 84" 6	\$110.00
Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 2:	Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 2	\$80.00
Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 3:	Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 3	\$80.00
Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 4:	Door-Interior-Single-Full Glass-Wood:3' 4	\$90.00
Grand total:	12	\$1220.00

Figure 29. Door Schedule with Total Cost

<Window Schedule>		
A	B	
Family and Type	Cost	
Fixed:16" x 24":	Fixed:16" x 24"	\$30.00
Fixed:16" x 24":	Fixed:16" x 24"	\$30.00
Skylight-Pyramid:17" x 36":	460451: Skylight-Pyramid:17" x 36":	460451
Slider with Trim 8":	Sliding Window: Slider with Trim:8" Sliding Window	\$90.00
Slider with Trim 8":	Sliding Window: Slider with Trim:8" Sliding Window	\$90.00
Slider with Trim 8":	Sliding Window: Slider with Trim:8" Sliding Window	\$90.00
Window-Bay-Casement-Box-90_Degree_Angle-Center_Fixed:	60" x 60" x 24"	\$30.00
Window-Bay-Casement-Box-90_Degree_Angle-Center_Fixed:	60" x 60" x 24"	\$35.00
Window-Double-Hung:4":	Window-Double-Hung:4"	\$40.00
Window-Double-Hung:4":	Window-Double-Hung:4"	\$40.00
Window-Fixed-Round-Top:18" x 27":	Window-Fixed-Round-Top:18" x 27"	\$35.00
Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 2:	Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 2	\$30.00
Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 30750:	Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 30750	\$35.00
Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 30990:	Window-Louvers:24" x 24" 30990	\$30.00

Figure 30. Window Schedule with Total Cost

Total Budget for RCC work, Doors & Windows, partition walls and Plastering 5,16,65,258.26 /-

To create a 5D BIM cost analysis in Navisworks

To incorporate cost information and create a 5D model, assign relevant properties to objects in BIM model to enable accurate quantity takeoffs and cost calculations. These properties include materials, labor rates, quantities, equipment or any other information required for estimating costs.

Then we need to link cost data to objects in BIM model. Navisworks supports the import of cost data from external sources like Excel spreadsheets or databases. Alternatively, we also manually assign costs to objects within Navisworks.

Utilize Navisworks' visualization and analysis features to review the project and identify potential clashes, constructability issues, or scheduling conflicts. You can simulate the construction process, analyze clashes, and optimize the schedule based on the 4D and 5D information.

Figure 31. 5D Building Information Modelling in Navisworks

Result and Discussion

An industry-changing development was the adoption of 5D BIM in construction project management. The introduction of 5D BIM increased the effectiveness of the construction process while also lowering project costs and duration. The information gathered during the building process was used to provide precise and accurate cost estimations, which improved project planning and administration.

Better communication and collaboration among the various parties engaged in the construction project were also made possible by the usage of 5D BIM. A more thorough understand of the project was offered by the 3D visualization capability and the additional dimensions of cost and time, which led to better decision-making and more effective project management.

Additionally, the use of 5D BIM reduced the possibility of mistakes during the construction phase by enabling the early detection and resolution of any conflicts and problems. Rework and waste were reduced as a result,

which further decreased the project's overall cost and duration.

The findings of this study unequivocally demonstrate the great benefits of implementing 5D BIM in construction project management. A more thorough understanding of the project is provided through the use of 5D BIM, allowing for better decision-making, enhanced project planning, and more effective project management.

The use of 5D BIM also lessens the possibility of mistakes during the construction phase by identifying and resolving any conflicts and concerns during the design phase. As a result, there is less waste and rework, which lowers the project's overall cost and duration.

The usage of 5D BIM also makes it easier for all parties engaged in the construction process to collaborate and communicate more effectively. With the extra dimensions of cost and time and the capacity to visualize the project in 3D, a more thorough picture of the project is provided, enabling better decision-making and more effective project management.

It should be highlighted that 5D BIM adoption requires a large investment in hardware, software, and training. Additionally, because old practices are so strongly established in the building sector, the implementation of 5D BIM requires a cultural change. Therefore, industry professionals that are not ready to change might be against the use of 5D BIM.

The advantages of 5D BIM exceed the drawbacks even with these difficulties. The adoption of 5D BIM in project management for construction projects is a step in the direction of a more effective, affordable, and sustainable construction sector. It is advised that construction firms implement 5D BIM and make the necessary financial investments to maximize its potential.

Conclusion

5D BIM is a potent tool for managing construction projects since it unifies numerous construction-related elements into a unified framework. Due to its capacity to improve project efficiency, accuracy, and collaboration,

this technology has been enthusiastically embraced by the construction industry.

According to the research findings presented in this paper, 5D BIM theory and practice have significant advantages for construction project management. These advantages include improved project visualization, decreased risk of errors and rework, improved cost and schedule control, and improved stakeholder collaboration and communication. Project managers may model various situations, spot possible problems before they arise, and make the most use of resources by using 5D BIM. Additionally, it makes it possible to create intricate construction timetables and to monitor development in real-time, both of which improve decision-making and raise the success rates of projects.

While there are many advantages to 5D BIM, there is a large time and resource investment needed to use this technology. A significant change in how building projects are managed and carried out is required by the implementation of 5D BIM, necessitating the development of new knowledge and skills.

Therefore, it is advised that project managers use 5D BIM gradually, beginning with a pilot project to determine the advantages and constraints of this technology. To guarantee that all stakeholders can utilize the technology successfully and benefit from it, it is also crucial to provide training to them.

In conclusion, 5D BIM is a crucial tool for managing construction projects since it facilitates better decision-making, cooperation, and communication. Despite the fact that its implementation demands a considerable investment, the advantages of this technology are great, making it an important resource for the building sector.

Author contributions

Md Masud Rana: investigation, funding acquisition, and writing

– original draft preparation, Yeasin Arafat: writing original draft preparation, data

analysis, Md Nishat Hasan: writing – review and editing, and checking the original

draft; Md Atik Hasan: writing – review and editing and checking the original draft.

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